

Characterization of microorganisms according to vaginal community state types microbiota: an observational study among women across Italy

Calugi G¹, Meschino N², Blandino F³, Bouba Y⁴, Giannico R⁵, Palma E⁶, Di Lullo M⁷, Brizi S⁸, Forlani L⁹, Armenia D¹⁰

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1. Genetic biologist - Department of Research and Development, Eurofins Genoma Group, Rome, Italy
ISIR ETS - International Society for Independent Research
2. Molecular biologist - Department of Research and Development, Eurofins Genoma Group, Rome, Italy
3. Molecular biologist - Department of Research and Development, Eurofins Genoma Group, Rome, Italy
4. Virologist - Saint Camillus International University of Health Sciences, Rome, Italy
5. Bioinformatician - Department of Bioinformatics, Eurofins Genoma Group, Italy
6. Medical doctor - Department of Maternal Infantile and Urological Sciences, Sapienza University of Rome, Rome, Italy
7. Biomedical laboratory technician - Department of Molecular Microbiology, Eurofins Genoma Group, Rome, Italy
8. Biomedical laboratory technician - Department of Molecular Microbiology, Eurofins Genoma Group, Rome, Italy
9. Bioinformatician - Department of Bioinformatics, Eurofins Genoma Group, Italy
10. Microbiologist - Saint Camillus International University of Health Sciences, Rome, Italy

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Corresponding author: Graziella Calugi - graziella.calugi@gmail.com

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Abstract

The vaginal Microbiome and composition of microbial flora play an important role in maintaining female health, and it's fluctuating during the women's entire life. The aim of this work is to characterize microbial composition and dysbiosis level in a large population of healthy, paucisymptomatic or symptomatic women.

Community State Type (CST) was assigned by a Lactobacilli Flora Genotyping Realtime PCR (RT-PCR, KIT vaginitis and vaginosis by AUS Diagnostic) and an in-house informatic Pipeline; other pathogens were detected by a commercial RT-PCR (Seegene, Alloplex Kits). Dysbiosis level according to CST was categorized in 3 groups: (I) Normal (N): CST I or CST II; (II) partially dysbiotic (PD): CST III or CST V; (III) dysbiotic (D): CST IV. Covariation analyses were performed to explore potential microorganisms interactions. Regression models (RM) were used to evaluate predictors of dysbiosis (D or PD) according to demographic, physiological and microbial detection.

Overall, 203 women with a median (IQR) age of 39 (34-55) were analysed. Of them, 50.2% were symptomatic, 70.4% at the reproductive state, 8.4% in menopause and 72.9% with normal BMI. Most individuals showed N level (48.8%), followed by PD (35.0%) and D (16.2%). At increasing dysbiosis level an older age was observed (D vs. PD vs. N: 44 [38-68] vs. 41 [34-51] vs. 37 [31-52], $p < 0.001$). The most frequent microorganisms were *Gardnerella vaginalis* (50.7%), *Atopobium vaginae* (33.5%), *Candida albicans* (24.6%); *Ureaplasma parvum* (23.6%) and *Streptococcus agalactiae* (19.7%). In about half of women (53.7%), ≥ 2 microorganisms were detected. Dysbiosis (PD or D levels) was significantly associated with the number of microorganisms detected (0, 1, ≥ 2 : 35.3%, 41.9%, 62.4%, $P = 0.002$). Compared to dysbiotic (PD or D level), in individuals with normal flora, *Gardnerella vaginalis* (41.7% vs. 58.3%, $P = 0.042$), *Ureaplasma parvum* (35.4% vs. 64.6%, $P = 0.034$), *Atopobium vaginae* (39.7% vs. 60.3%, $P = 0.067$) and *Candida albicans* (19.2% vs. 29.8%, $P = 0.079$) were not frequent. As expected, microorganisms were often associated to each other. However, the pathogenic *Streptococcus agalactiae* significantly correlated only with *Candida albicans*, with a correlation frequency of 42.5% ($\Phi = 0.205$, $P = 0.003$). According to RM, older age (per 5-years increase, OR 95 C.I.: 1.4 [1.2-1.7], $P < 0.001$) and presence of *Candida albicans* (2.3 [1.1-4.6] $P = 0.019$) independently predicted dysbiosis.

In this observational study, about half of individuals showed normal vaginal microbiota. Older age and the presence of multiple microorganisms, in particular *Candida albicans* were predictive of dysbiotic vaginal flora.

Keywords

Vaginal microbiota, Community State Types (CST), Vaginal dysbiosis, Molecular diagnostics, Real-time PCR (RT-PCR)

Introduction

The female lower reproductive tract hosts a complex and dynamic micro-ecosystem of microbes known as the vaginal microbiota (VMB), which plays a crucial role in maintaining a woman's health and protecting from infectious diseases [2]. The composition of VMB is continually fluctuating during a woman's life span due to behavioural changes such diet; and intrinsic factors such as race, hormonal fluctuations, pregnancy and menopause [3, 18, 19]. The disruption of the VMB equilibrium leads to a polymicrobial vaginal microenvironment, potentially resulting in diseases such as bacterial vaginosis [17].

The advent of molecular methods have helped to overcome the limitations of microscopic and culture-based approaches [20], thereby furthering the understanding of the complex vaginal microbial composition. Today, it is known that, throughout the woman reproductive age, a healthy VMB is mainly composed of *Lactobacillus*, which maintain the typical acidic vaginal microenvironment and produce other antimicrobial compounds; both playing a key role in restricting the growth of other pathogenic microorganisms [2, 8, 15]. Even though several species of *Lactobacillus* exist, unlike any other anatomical site on the human body, vaginal communities are generally dominated by one of the *Lactobacillus* spp. In this regard, there are five major groups of vaginal microbial communities, referred to as community state types (CST). Four CST are dominated by *Lactobacillus* iners, *L. crispatus*, *L. gasseri*, or *L. jensenii*, whereas the fifth has lower proportions of lactic acid bacteria and higher proportions of strictly anaerobic organisms [2, 24]. This same study found that, in women of reproductive age, CST group I occurred in 26.2% of the women, and were dominated by *L. crispatus*; whereas groups II, III, and V were dominated by *L. gasseri*, *L. iners*, and *L. jensenii*, respectively.

On the other hand, CST group IV forms a heterogeneous microbial community which is dominated by polymicrobial

flora including *Lactobacillus* and bacterial vaginosis-associated anaerobic bacteria species such as *Gardnerella* and *Atopobium*, with or without *Lactobacillus* species [14, 24, 29]. CST IV generally indicates vaginal dysbiosis, potentially leading to colonization by pathogenic bacteria.

A VMB dominated by *L. crispatus* has been generally described to be related with healthy status, limiting the infections by other bacteria [13, 24, 29]. It should be however noted that the VMB is dynamic and influenced by a variety of factors; for instance, normal VMB in Caucasians and Asian women are more likely to be dominated by *Lactobacillus* spp., when compared to black and Hispanic women [2, 28]. The vaginal microbial community is also rich in anaerobic bacteria including *Gardnerella vaginalis*, *Prevotella* spp., *Mobiluncus* spp., *Ureaplasma urealyticum*, and *Mycoplasma hominis* [14, 24]. It is thought that the VMB plays a role in modulating the infection by Human papillomavirus, *Chlamydia trachomatis*, *Neisseria gonorrhoea* and *Mycoplasma genitalium* infections among the others [27].

Several laboratory methods such as the Nugent scoring or the Amsel's criteria exist to study VMB, however, in the recent years, molecular techniques provides more insight into this complex microbial environment [20, 21, 24]. However, more data are needed to characterize the vaginal microbial environment according to CST in women presenting with symptoms or not. In fact, previous works advocated for more studies based on genomics to improve our understanding of possible interactions and pathogenesis of some diseases which is still unclear [16].

Therefore, shedding lights on the covariation between these bacteria using metagenomics assays might be useful to understand possible interactions and disease patterns. The aim of this work is to characterize microbial composition and dysbiosis status in a large population of healthy and symptomatic women.

Materials and methods

Ethic statement

All procedures in this study were conducted in accordance with the Helsinki Declaration.

The study was further approved by the Eurofins Internal Ethical committee (protocol number: PR 08 F6). All women signed an informed consent for the collection and the use of personal information along with clinical data to be used and published in an anonymized way for research purpose.

Study cohort and sample collection

Our observational study was conducted in a group of 203 women in reproductive age both healthy and symptomatic for urogenital issues, like leucorrhea, vaginal itching or dyspareunia in which vaginal microbiota was evaluated.

All patients has been enrolled as routine testing from clinicians to valuate the vaginal microbiota assessment or for pregnancy planning or due to cervicovaginal symptoms evaluation. Vaginal swabs were collected through soft and small FLOQSwabs® tip for a painless collection. These swabs are a sterile dry format that can be stored until bacterial DNA extraction. Total DNA was later extracted from vaginal samples using the QIAAsymphony® DSP Virus/Pathogen Kit following the manufacturer's instructions (QIAGEN).

Real time PCR

DNA extracted was later amplified through CE-IVD Real Time AUS Diagnostics Highplex 24 kit for the determination of the following microorganisms: *Trichomonas vaginalis*, *Candida parapsilosis*, *Gardnerella vaginalis*, *Atopobium vaginae*, *Candida albicans*, *Candida glabrata*, *Candida krusei*, *Chlamydia trachomatis*, *Mycoplasma genitalium*, *Mycoplasma hominis*, *Neisseria gonorrhoeae*, *Streptococcus agalactiae*, *Ureaplasma parvum*, *Ureaplasma urealyticum*.

Targeted amplification of the 16S rDNA gene region was performed by qPCR using the Vaginitis and Vaginosis 12-well panel (AusDiagnostics), following the manufacturer's instructions (Nuclear Laser Medicine).

Data analysis and bioinformatics

An automatic procedure was set up to collect patients data coming from multiple technologies and merge them to build a full prospect of each sample. Later, rules were applied to these profiles to obtain a classification.

Presence or absence of microorganisms was called using custom thresholds over the PCR cycles count provided by vendor's softwares. Community State Type was determined based on the concentration of *lactobacilli* as pointed out by the realtime system by AUS Diagnostic.

Results from the machine were validated by a human operator and then processed using an in-house python algorithm. Samples with invalid exogenous or endogenous controls were discarded and labeled as not classifiable. For each sample, the algorithm assigns the CST associated with the most present *lactobacilli*, given that a minimum concentration threshold fixed at 1e4 amplification cycles (CT), is hit. Since the eubiosis-dysbiosis complex has a dynamic nature, a situation of transient CST can also happen and it is identified by the presence of two *lactobacilli* simultaneously. In this case, the most present is considered as the primary CST, while the other is the secondary (residual or upcoming). On the contrary, absence of *lactobacilli* ends up in a CST IV classification.

Statistical analyses

All the analyses were performed using the software package SPSS version 26.0 for Windows (SPSS Inc., Chicago, Illinois). Categorical variables were presented as number (proportions), while continuous variables were presented as median (interquartile range). The associations between CST and individuals' characteristics and microorganisms' prevalence were investigated by Chi-Squared or Kruskal-Wallis test, as appropriate. Dysbiosis

level according to CST was categorized in 3 groups: (I) Normal (N): CST I or CST II; (II) partially dysbiotic (PD): CST III or CST V; (III) dysbiotic (D): CST IV. Covariation analyses were performed to explore potential microorganisms interactions. In particular, the binomial correlation coefficient (phi) was used to assess covariation among the microorganisms that were detected in analysed samples. All the detected microorganisms with a prevalence of ≥5% were considered for the covariation analysis. A positive and statistically significant correlation between microorganisms ($0.15 \geq \phi < 1, p < 0.05$) indicated that these two microorganisms are potentially related and have the tendency to co-evolve together.

A multivariate binary logistic regression was performed to evaluate the predictors of dysbiosis (D or PD) according to demographic, physiological parameters and detection of microorganisms typically related with vaginal infection (as described above). Conditional backward stepwise regression models were built to assess variables significantly associated with dysbiosis level. The number of microorganisms and the specific microorganisms were evaluated in separated models. Variables with p values greater than 0.05 are retained and those with p values less 0.10 were retained in multivariable models.

Results

1. Population characteristics stratified according to CST

Overall, 203 women with a median (IQR) age of 39 (34-55) were analysed (Table 1). All participants who provided informed consent completed a structured questionnaire collecting demographic and clinical information, including age, body mass index, clinical indications, and associated symptoms.

Of them, 50.2% had a least one vaginal related symptoms as vaginal itching, leucorrhoea among minor others (Fig. 1). About 70.4% of them were at the reproductive state, 8.4% in menopause and 1.5% were pregnant. Most of them (72.9%)

had a normal body mass index (BMI).

Concerning CST, most of the women showed normal vaginal microbiota (48.8%), followed by those who showed partial dysbiosis (35.0%) and complete dysbiosis (16.2%). According to CST, women in dysbiotic group were significantly older in non-reproductive age compared to those who did not showed dysbiosis (Table 1, $P < 0.05$).

A small rate of samples was reported as inconclusive 2,4% due to low rate of sampling cells leading to a low extracted DNA (<1ng/ml).

Variables	Community State Type II / Vaginal flora status				p-value
	Total (N=203)	1 or 2 Normal (N =99)	3 or 5 Partial dysbiotic (N=71)	4 Dysbiotic (N=33)	
Age, median (IQR)	39 (34-55)	37 (31-52)	41 (34-51)	44 (38-68)	<0.001
Vaginal symptom, n (%)					0.670
Asymptomatic	78 (38.4)	39 (39.4)	29 (40.8)	10 (30.3)	
Symptomatic	102 (50.2)	50 (50.5)	35 (49.3)	17 (51.5)	
Unknown	23 (11.3)	10 (10.1)	7 (9.9)	6 (18.2)	
Physiological condition, n (%)					0.010
Reproductive state	143 (70.4)	76 (76.8)	53 (74.6)	14 (42.4)	
Menopause	17 (8.4)	5 (5.1)	5 (7.0)	7 (21.2)	
Pregnant	3 (1.5)	1 (1.0)	1 (1.4)	1 (3.0)	
Unknown	40 (19.7)	17 (17.2)	12 (16.9)	11 (33.3)	
Body Mass Index, n (%)					0.053
Normal weight	148 (72.9)	78 (78.8)	50 (70.4)	20 (60.6)	
Overweight	17 (8.4)	7 (7.1)	7 (9.9)	3 (9.1)	
Underweight	10 (4.9)	6 (6.1)	4 (5.6)	0 (0.0)	
Unknown	28 (13.8)	8 (8.1)	10 (14.1)	10 (30.3)	

Table 1 - Population characteristics stratified by Community State Type I - IQR: interquartile range. CST was determined by internal developed algorithm.

Figure 1 - Relative CST weights related to different clinical symptoms.

2. Prevalence of detected microorganisms and their combinations according to CST

In Table 2 prevalence of microorganisms detected according to dysbiosis levels is reported. The most frequently detected bacteria (above 5%) were *G. vaginalis*, followed by *A. vaginae*, *U. parvum*, *S. agalactiae* and *U. urealyticum*, while *C. trachomatis*, *N. gonorrhoea*, *M. hominis* and *M.*

genitalium were rarely detected. Regarding fungi, *C. albicans* was the most frequent species (24.6%); but species such as *C. glabrata*, *C. parapsilosis* and *C. krusei* were also detected in some patients (<5%). The prevalence of *G. vaginalis*, *A. vaginae* and *U. parvum* was significantly higher in women with partial dysbiosis.

Detected microorganisms in metagenomic test	Community State Type // Vaginal flora status				p-value
	Total (N=203)	1 or 2 Normal (N=99)	3 or 5 Partial dysbiotic (N=71)	4 Dysbiotic (N=33)	
<i>Gardnerella vaginalis</i>	103 (50.7)	43 (43.4)	49 (69.0)	11 (33.3)	<0.001
<i>Atopobium vaginae</i>	68 (33.5)	27 (27.3)	33 (46.5)	8 (24.2)	0.015
<i>Candida albicans</i>	50 (24.6)	19 (19.2)	23 (32.4)	8 (24.2)	0.143
<i>Streptococcus agalactiae</i>	40 (19.7)	18 (18.2)	15 (21.1)	7 (21.2)	0.868
<i>Ureaplasma parvum</i>	48 (23.6)	17 (17.2)	27 (38.0)	4 (12.1)	0.002
<i>Ureaplasma urealyticum</i>	11 (5.4)	4 (4.0)	7 (9.9)	0 (0.0)	0.083
<i>Mycoplasma hominis</i>	9 (4.4)	4 (4.0)	5 (7.0)	0 (0)	0.258
Other microorganisms	23 (11.3)	9 (9.1)	11 (15.5)	3 (9.1)	0.390

Table 2 - Prevalence of detected microorganisms, overall and according to CST - All the microorganisms with a prevalence <4.4% were grouped into "other" microorganisms, and included: *C. trachomatis* (n=5), *C. parapsilosis* (n=7), *C. glabrata* (n=4), *C. krusei* (n=4), *M. genitalium* (n=5), *N. gonorrhoeae* (n=5)

In addition, the number of microorganisms co-infection was associated with dysbiosis state (Figure 2).

As shown in Figure 1, an increase in the number of detected microorganisms corresponded to a significant decline in the proportion of individuals with normal flora and a rise in those with partial dysbiosis (Figure 1, P<0.05). Complete dysbiosis also varied with microorganism count,

showing a trend toward significance (P=0.090), and was less frequent in individuals harboring three or more microorganisms (6.7%) than in those with fewer than three (20.3%, P=0.016).

To summarize, as the degree of partially dysbiosis versus dysbiosis increases, the number of microorganisms involved in coinfection also rises."

Figure 2 - Association between dysbiosis level and number of microorganisms detected in vaginal samples. P value according with Chi-Squared test.

Considering that coinfection was common, the combination of microorganisms detected is reported in Table 3. For instance, the detection of *G. vaginalis* was strongly correlated with *A. vaginae*, *M. hominis*, *U. parvum* and *U.*

urealyticum. *S. agalactiae* and *C. albicans* were significantly correlated and a considerable proportion of *S. agalactiae* was detected together with *C. albicans* (42.5%, $\Phi=0.205$, $p=0.003$).

Microorganisms	Frequency, n (%)	Correlated microorganisms	N	Covariation frequency ^a , n (%)	Phi	P-Value
Gardnerella vaginalis	103 (50.7)	Atopobium vaginae	68	56 (82.5)	0.449	<0.001
		Mycoplasma hominis	9	9 (100)	0.212	0.002
		Ureaplasma parvum	48	37 (77.1)	0.293	<0.001
		Ureaplasma urealyticum	11	11 (100)	0.236	0.001
Candida Albicans	50 (24.6)	Streptococcus agalactiae	40	17 (42.5)	0.205	0.003

Table 3 - Microorganisms' covariation. A positive and statistically significant correlation between microorganisms ($0.15 \phi < 1$, $P < 0.05$) indicates that these two microorganisms are co-present with potential synergism. a Frequency of microorganisms in overall population (N=203). b Proportion within the correlated microorganisms.

Variables	Odd ratio to detected dysbiotic vaginal flora					
	Crude		Adjusted 1 ^a		Adjusted 2 ^b	
	P Value	Odd ratio (95% C.I.)	P Value	Odd ratio (95% C.I.)	P Value	Odd ratio (95% C.I.)
Age, per five years increase	<0.001	1.4 (1.1-1.6)	<0.001	1.4 (1.2-1.7)	<0.001	1.4 (1.2-1.7)
Symptoms						
Asymptomatic	0.858	1.0				
Symptomatic	0.896	1 (0.6-1.9)				
Unknown	0.583	1.3 (0.5-3.3)				
Physiological condition						
Reproductive state		1.0				
Menopause	0.073	2.7 (0.9-8.1)				
Pregnant	0.508	2.3 (0.2-25.6)				
Unknown	0.236	1.5 (0.8-3.1)				
BMI						
Underweight		1.0				
Normal weight	0.371	1.6 (0.6-4.4)				
Overweight	0.655	0.7 (0.2-2.7)				
Unknown	0.023	2.8 (1.2-6.7)				
Bowel condition						
Normal		1.0				
Styptic	0.766	1.1 (0.5-2.6)				
Styptic/diarrhoeic	0.251	0.3 (0-2.6)				
Diarrhoeic	0.295	0.5 (0.1-2)				
Unknown	0.456	1.3 (0.6-2.8)				
N. microorganisms detected						
0		1.0				
1	0.515	1.3 (0.6-3)			0.501	1.4 (0.6-3.3)
2	0.002	3.8 (1.7-8.7)			0.001	4.6 (1.9-11.1)
≥3	0.016	2.6 (1.2-5.5)			0.006	3.2 (1.4-7.2)
<i>Gardnerella vaginalis</i>	0.043	1.8 (1.3-3.1)	0.091	1.7 (0.9-3.1)	-	-
<i>Atopobium vaginae</i>	0.068	1.7 (1-3.1)			-	-
<i>Candida albicans</i>	0.081	1.8 (0.9-3.4)	0.019	2.3 (1.1-4.6)	-	-
<i>Mycoplasma hominis</i>	0.791	1.2 (0.3-4.6)			-	-
<i>Streptococcus agalactiae</i>	0.595	1.2 (0.6-2.4)			-	-
<i>Ureaplasma parvum</i>	0.036	2 (1-4)	0.071	2.0 (0.9-4.1)	-	-
<i>Ureaplasma urealyticum</i>	0.402	1.7 (0.5-6)			-	-
Other microorganisms	0.329	1.6 (0.6-3.8)			-	-

Table 4 - Predictors of dysbiosis in vaginal microbiota. Multi-variables models were built including variables according to stepwise backward conditional selection. The number of microorganisms and the specific microorganisms were evaluated in separated models. ^aAdjusted for specific microorganisms detected; ^bAdjusted for the number of microorganisms detected.

3. Factors associated with dysbiosis

To assess potential predictors of dysbiosis unimultivariable logistic regression models were built (Table 4). Concerning individual's characteristics, only an older age was a predictor of dysbiosis ($P < 0.001$). The presence of at least two microorganisms significantly increased the risk of detecting dysbiosis.

Discussion

This work aimed at characterizing microbial composition and dysbiosis status using molecular techniques in a population of both healthy and symptomatic women living in Italy. Most of the participants showed a Lactobacillus dominated VMB (about 84%), as observed in similar settings of Caucasians women [2, 15, 24, 29, 31]. This proportion is high when compared to other ethnic groups such as Hispanic and Black women who have generally a polymicrobial VMB [5, 12, 15]. In the present study, almost half of the women had a normal VMB (CST I & CST II); this number was reported at lower percentage in other studies [15, 24]. On the other hand, partially dysbiotic (CST III & V) and dysbiotic (CST IV) VMB represented about 35% and 16%, respectively. The proportion of partially dysbiotic state which is the combination of VMB dominated by *L. iners* and *L. jensenii* is consistent with findings from other studies [11]. The proportion of dysbiotic VMB (CST IV) observed in this study is the double of what was reported by Ravel and collaborators (9.3%) [24]. This difference might be justified by the fact that our study included menopausal women, as well as presenting with a symptom. In fact, this study confirmed that age is an independent predictor of a dysbiotic VMB.

Moreover, when correlating the Community State Types with the reported symptomatology (Fig. 1), it becomes evident that CST3 and CST4 increase in prevalence with greater symptom severity. In particular, a pronounced dysbiosis, represented by CST4, is associated with the presence of itching and dyspareunia, as shown in Figure 1. Community State Type 3, indicative of an early stage of dysbiosis, is more frequently observed in individuals reporting symptoms such as dyspareunia and the urinary tract itching.

Beside CST characterization, several other commensal, opportunistic and pathogenic microorganisms were detected in this study. The more common ones (>5%) were *G. vaginalis*, *A. vaginae*, *U. parvum*, *S. agalactiae* and *U. urealyticum* and *C. albicans* that showed the highest prevalence all in a context of partial dysbiosis (CST III or V). Specifically, *G. vaginalis* was present in half of the samples, with a significantly higher prevalence (69%) in the VMB dominated by partially dysbiotic state (CST III & V), followed by normal state (43%).

An important consideration on *Gardnerella vaginalis* in normal patients (43%) is that the used molecular test in this study is detecting *Gardnerella vaginalis* at the genus level and does not discriminate among species or clades that differ in pathogenic potential. This analytical feature can maybe contributes to the observation of a high prevalence of *Gardnerella* in asymptomatic, eubiotic patients, reflecting the presence of non-pathogenic or low-virulence strains.

In fact, previous studies reported that *G. vaginalis* may not

In particular, *C. albicans* was the only microorganisms which predicts vaginal dysbiosis (AOR [95% C.I.]: 2.3 [1.1-4.6], $P = 0.019$) while *G. vaginalis* (AOR [95% C.I.]: 1.7 [0.9-3.1], $P = 0.091$) and *U. parvum* (AOR [95% C.I.]: 2.0 [0.9-4.1], $P = 0.071$) were associated with an increased risk of dysbiosis with a trend toward significance.

be part of normal VMB in women with optimal vaginal health and it is the most common microorganism identified from bacterial vaginosis. It is associated with CST IV and CST III in which vaginal infections are more likely to develop [7, 11, 25, 26]. However, *G. vaginalis* was less frequently observed in women with CST IV in the present study. Like *G. vaginalis*, a similar trend was observed for *A. vaginae* and *U. urealyticum*, which were both less frequent in dysbiotic VMB. This is in line with other studies which found that *A. vaginae* are associated with a microenvironment with low numbers of *lactobacilli* such CST III. Generally, the vaginal microbiota including *G. vaginalis*, *U. urealyticum* and *C. albicans* are associated with dysbiosis and might result is able in bacterial vaginosis (BV) [1, 5, 19, 29].

Interestingly, even though no significant difference was found according to CST, in our population, about 20% of women harboured *S. agalactiae* in vaginal flora. Concerning other pathogenic bacteria, *C. trachomatis*, *N. gonorrhoea*, *M. hominis* and *M. genitalium* were detected at low frequency (<5%) regardless the dysbiosis status.

As expected, *C. albicans* was the most frequent (25%) fungus detected, but other *Candida* species such as *C. glabrata*, *C. parapsilosis* and *C. Krusei* were also detected (<5%) in some women, confirming the results of other studies [15, 16]. In the literature, the frequency of *C. albicans*, which is considered an opportunistic microorganism, varies according to laboratory methods used [20] and study population characteristics such as pregnancy (about 41%), asymptomatic individuals (about 20%) or presence of recurrent vulvovaginitis conditions (85-95%) [4, 15, 23, 24]. Even though not significant, our findings which show a more frequent detection of *C. albicans* in partially dysbiotic and dysbiotic condition confirms the observation that microbiota arbitrates the tolerance to colonisation by this species. In fact, it is known that *L. crispatus* reduce the virulence of *C. albicans* and enhances colonisation resistance by modulating the immune response [15].

Moreover, beyond the mere presence of single microorganism, we have observed that co-infection by at least 2 of them significantly increased especially in the samples of women with CST III or CST V (Figure 1). In fact, women with two detected microorganisms had 5 times odds of presenting with dysbiotic state (Table 4). This indicates that the presence of *L. iners* and *L. jensenii* might be less resistant to colonization by other bacteria such as *C. trachomatis*, as suggested by some reports [9]. Furthermore, our study found that the detection of *G. vaginalis* was strongly correlated with the coinfection by other bacteria such *A. vaginae* (83%), *M. hominis* (100%), *U. parvum* (77%) and *U. urealyticum* (100%) (Table 3). In fact, due to the low competition induced by the absence of *Lactobacillus*, *G. vaginalis* will predominate, forming a consortia of

polymicrobial environment with these bacteria [2, 6, 10]. It was interesting to find that *C. albicans* only strongly and positively correlated with *S. agalactiae* (at a frequency of up to 43%). Previous study reported co-occurrence of *C. albicans* and *Ureaplasma* genera of 20% [4]. In addition, it is known that that *S. agalactiae* inhibits *C. albicans* hyphal development, their co-association depends on the

expression of specific antigens and this interaction between them may affect the vaginal mucosal immunity [16, 22, 30]. The main limitation of this study is related to the insufficient clinical data to better characterise the CST as well as detected commensals and opportunistic microorganisms according to the presence or absence of specific symptoms.

Conclusions

In conclusion, our findings show that in Italy, the majority of VMB is dominated by *Lactobacillus* spp., half of them have a normal VMB (dominated by *L. crispatus* or *L. gasseri*), even though some were symptomatic. Microorganisms such as *Gardnerella vaginalis*, *Atopobium vaginae*, *Ureaplasma parvum*, *U. urealyticum* and *M. hominis* covariated among themselves, and their detected number was increased in

dysbiosis. An interesting finding that deserves further in-depth study is that *S. agalactiae* significantly correlated only with *C. albicans* which we found as an independent predictor of dysbiosis. Further studies are needed to evaluate the impact of microbes interaction in a context of different CST detected in vaginal microbiota.

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